

Defect-induced channel blockage drives propene and propane separation in PCR zeolites

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ABSTRACT

PCR zeolites display an unusually high kinetic selectivity in propene/propane separation. However, both propene and propane should diffuse freely through the ideal PCR framework, according to our molecular simulations. This discrepancy may be explained by foreign species introduced to the PCR channel system during the synthesis. To test this hypothesis, we synthesized 10 × 8-ring PCR zeolites by Assembly-Disassembly-Organization-Reassembly (ADOR) and assessed propene/propane adsorptive separation on these small-pore zeolitic materials using experimental (volumetric and spectroscopic measurements) and computational methods (Density Functional Theory (DFT) and Force Field (FF) calculations). Whether by in-situ FTIR with the pivalonitrile probe or by MAS NMR with the shift reagent, we detected a particularly high concentration of hydroxyl groups specifically in PCR micropores. These defects partly block the 10-ring channels, forcing mass transport through the smaller 8-ring channels, which becomes the rate-determining step. As a result, PCR microporous adsorbents match the performance of other zeolites, such as DDR, IHW, and ITE, contradicting computational predictions. These findings highlight adsorption on PCR zeolites as a sustainable alternative to energy-intensive separations of light hydrocarbon mixtures. Moreover, a comprehensive approach to controlling impurity location in pores during synthesis may yield adsorbents with optimal properties for real-world applications in the petroleum industry.

1. Introduction

In the chemical industry, one of the most energy-intensive processes is the separation of light olefin/paraffin mixtures. Due to their small differences in kinetic diameters, relative volatility, and boiling points, they can only be fractionated under cryogenic conditions and at higher pressures (15 – 35 atm) in large distillation towers with over 100 trays [1–3]. Making matters worse, the consumption of light olefins, such as ethene, propene, butene isomers, and butadiene [2], continues to increase, primarily for the production of plastics. In this context, further research is needed to develop alternative, less energy-intensive separation processes.

Among viable, more energy-sustainable alternatives, adsorption on various microporous materials, such as MOFs, ZIFs, porous carbons, and zeolites, offers a promising route for light olefin/paraffin separation. For example, MOFs have recently demonstrated exceptional potential *via*

“pore engineering” strategies; for instance, the use of quasi-discrete pore environments can precisely regulate the diffusion of olefins and paraffins, leveraging a synergistic thermodynamic–kinetic effect to achieve high selectivity [4]. Similarly, the pore size and architecture of carbon molecular sieves can be tailored to provide diffusion-gated discrimination between olefin and paraffin molecules [5]. While these materials allow for high performance, for example *via* structural tailoring [4–7], the more robust and stable inorganic zeolitic materials often remain the preferred choice for demanding industrial conditions due to their superior chemical and thermal durability [8–11].

Generally, zeolites enable selective adsorption by leveraging differences in the adsorption affinity of gas molecules for the adsorbent (equilibrium mechanism) or in molecular size and shape, leading to transport restrictions and even exclusion of some molecules from their pores (kinetic mechanism) [8–11]. Numerous zeolites have been tested for equilibrium-based olefin/paraffin separation, most frequently

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zeolites containing extra-framework cations, such as LTA (4A [12–15], 5A [15–17], Ag-A [18]), FAU (13X [13,15,16], CuNa-X [19], Na-Y [20], Ag-Y [20,21], Cu-Y [22]), FER (Li-, Na-, K-FER [23]), or for example the related ion-exchanged ETS-4 [24] and ETS-10 [25] materials.

Small-pore, pure-silica zeolites, which discriminate between molecules based on their kinetic diameters, display, however, the highest selectivity [26–35]. These materials provide, furthermore, additional advantages, including the absence of strong active sites that could catalyze oligomerization reactions (and lead to coking) or competitively attract polar gas impurities (e.g., carbon dioxide, hydrogen sulfide, nitrogen oxides, and water). These zeolites also boast relatively large pore volumes as their channels remain unoccupied by potentially bulky extra-framework cations [8]. One such material is the high-silica germanosilicate PCR zeolite [36], also known as IPC-4. PCR zeolite can be synthesized from the germanosilicate UTL precursor [37,38] by Assembly-Disassembly-Organization-Reassembly (ADOR) [36,39,40]. The PCR zeolite contains a two-dimensional channel system characterized by intersecting perpendicular 10- and 8-ring channels (see Fig. 1) running parallel along large, sheet-like crystals, with pore entrances only on their narrow edges. Both types of channels are characterized by windows of comparable sizes to those of materials which are known to exhibit very selective behavior for the propene/propane mixtures (such as CHA [27,28], DDR [26–28], IHW [29], and ITE [27,28]), combined with the crystal morphology suitable for maximizing mass transport-related effects. Therefore, PCR zeolite may be suitable for kinetics-driven separation of these hydrocarbons.

In this study, we investigated the ability of PCR zeolite to separate propene and propane experimentally and computationally. Multiple, independently synthesized, PCR batches were tested for propene and propane adsorption in volumetric experiments. The quantitative results were subsequently discussed in light of structural aspects, spectroscopic results (in-situ FTIR, MAS NMR), and computational predictions. Based on these results, we propose a mechanism that explains the high performance of PCR zeolite.

2. Methods

2.1. Synthesis and characterization

This study was performed on a set of four PCR zeolite batches (denoted as PCR-1, -2, -3, and -4), all of which were synthesized under the same conditions, according to a protocol previously reported in the literature [36]. In addition, SBA-15 mesoporous silica, H-FAU zeolite, and GeO₂ (supplied by Sigma, product no. 199478) were used as standards in spectroscopic measurements. The synthesis of all materials is described in more detail in the Supplementary Information (SI).

The crystallinity and purity of the materials were assessed by the powder X-ray diffraction (PXRD) on a Bruker AXS-D8 Advance diffractometer (CuK α radiation, $\lambda = 1.5406 \text{ \AA}$), employing the Bragg-Brentano geometry.

Scanning electron microscopy (SEM) images were recorded with a Tescan LYRA 3 microscope equipped with an AZtec X-Max 20 EDS analyzer from Oxford Instruments, operated at an acceleration voltage of 20 kV.

N₂ adsorption/desorption isotherms were measured at 77.3 K on a Micromeritics ASAP 2020 Plus high-performance adsorption analyzer. Prior to each experiment, the samples were thermally treated under dynamic vacuum at 523 K for 6 h. Micropore volume and specific surface area were determined using the t-plot and BET methods, according to IUPAC recommendations [42].

To precisely determine the unit cell dimensions of the material, additional PXRD experiments were performed in the more appropriate Debye-Scherrer geometry (with glass capillaries 0.7 mm in diameter) on a Rigaku MiniFlex 600 benchtop diffractometer (CuK α radiation, $\lambda = 1.5406 \text{ \AA}$). PXRD patterns were optimized using the Le Bail refinement procedure to determine lattice parameters. Additional information is provided in the SI.

The presence and location of silanol groups, as well as the nature of the acidic sites within the micropore system, were investigated by FTIR on a Nicolet 6700 FTIR spectrometer equipped with an MCT/A cryodetector, connected to a home-made transmission setup. For this purpose, the samples were dispersed, fixed on KBr wafers, and thermally pretreated in-situ under dynamic vacuum for 90 min at 523 K.

Fig. 1. Schematic representation of a PCR crystal [41] with projections along the (001) and along the (010) planes, showing the characteristic 8- and 10-rings.

Pivalonitrile and D₃-acetonitrile adsorption was measured at room temperature and at an equilibrium pressure of 6 torr (equilibration time >15 min). The findings from pivalonitrile adsorption were independently confirmed by NMR on a JEOL ECZ 600 MHz spectrometer with the shift reagent d²⁷-[Eu(fod)₃] to selectively mask specific signals of the NMR spectra. The FTIR and NMR methodologies are described in more detail in the SI.

2.2. Adsorption investigation

Single-component propene and propane adsorption isotherms and uptake curves were both measured on a Micromeritics ASAP 2020 Plus high-performance surface area analyzer. Adsorption isotherms were measured over a pressure range of 0 – 800 torr. The adsorption equilibrium threshold was set at < 0.01% pressure change on a 30 s interval. The uptake curve measurements were performed on a single dose – the procedure consisted of expanding ~ 62 torr of gas from the manifold of approx. 45.4 cm³ (~303 K) into the evacuated sample space (~20 cm³), resulting in an equilibrium pressure of approximately 25 – 35 torr in all experiments. Both types of experiments were performed at the sample temperature of exactly 303.15 K. The temperature of the sample tube was controlled by a Peltier thermostat equipped with a Pt sensor (supplied by e-Lab services, Czech Republic; temperature control accuracy ± 0.1 K). Before each experiment, the sample (ca. 75 mg of dry sample) was heated at 523 K for 6 h under dynamic vacuum. The temperature program consisted of heating from room temperature to 383 K at 0.5 K/min, maintaining the temperature at 383 K for 60 min before heating to the final temperature by 2.5 K/min. Supplied by Gerling Holz & Co (GHC), 99.95% propene and 99.97% propane were used in all experiments without further purification.

In addition to these experiments, the regenerability of the materials was investigated by in-situ FTIR experiments (employing the same setup as the one described above). These experiments consisted of dosing approx. 42 torr of propene (equilibration time – 40 min) and then capturing spectra upon evacuation for 90 min.

The apparent propene and propane diffusivities (D/R^2) were estimated from the volumetric/manometric uptake curves by fitting the experimental data with the following two models, recommended by Kärger et al. [43,44]:

The simple \sqrt{t} -law, valid for the low-uptake limit of the uptake curve:

$$\frac{n(t) - n(0)}{n(\infty) - n(0)} = \frac{p(0) - p(-0)}{p(\infty) - p(-0)} 6 \sqrt{\frac{Dt}{\pi R^2}}$$

and more general model, valid for the uptake curve in its full range:

$$\frac{n(t) - n(0)}{n(\infty) - n(0)} = 1 - \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{6\lambda(\lambda + 1)}{9 + 9\lambda + q_n^2 \lambda^2} \exp\left(-q_n^2 \frac{D}{R^2} t\right)$$

where $\lambda = p(\infty)/[p(0) - p(\infty)]$, and q_n denotes the positive nonzero roots of:

$$\tan q_n = \frac{3q_n}{3 + \lambda q_n^2}$$

In these models, $n(t)$ and $p(t)$ stand for the adsorbed amount and pressure at time t ; $n(\infty)$ and $p(\infty)$, for equilibrium uptake and pressure; $n(0)$ and $p(-0)$, for adsorbed amount and pressure in the sample chamber before the process; $p(0)$, for the pressure at time 0 (corresponding to only gas expansion and no adsorption); and D/R^2 , for the apparent diffusion coefficient of the gas.

Employing the \sqrt{t} -law, the diffusivity values were obtained from the initial slopes of the $n(t) = f(\sqrt{t})$ curves, along with the values of $n(0)$, which were likewise optimized. Due to the inability to determine the $n(\infty)$ of slowly adsorbing propane, the equilibrium uptake of propene was employed when calculating the propane diffusivity. For the general

model, the curves were fitted in MS Excel using the Solver tool, as $n(t) = f(t)$ curves. The calculation involved obtaining the q_n parameters for each term of the sum, which was performed by the Newton method on a separate sheet of the Excel file. The infinite sum was approximated by its first 200 terms. The optimization was performed for the D/R^2 and $n(\infty)$ parameters only (the $n(0)$ were fixed to the values determined from the \sqrt{t} -law).

2.3. Computational investigation

Slow diffusion of propene and propane at the zero-coverage limit was evaluated using the Bennett-Chandler approach [45].

$$k_{A \rightarrow B} = \kappa \cdot \sqrt{\frac{k_B T}{2 \pi m}} \int_{\text{cage A}} \frac{\exp[-F(\xi^*)/(k_B T)]}{\exp[-F(\xi)/(k_B T)]} d\xi'$$

where the free energy profiles, F , were obtained from well-tempered metadynamics simulations employing an NpT-averaged cell in the NVT ensemble (see details in the SI). The diffusion coefficients were calculated from the hopping rates using the jump length, λ , in the respective directions (along the main and side channels)

$$D_{A \rightarrow B} = k_{A \rightarrow B} \cdot \lambda^2$$

3. Results and discussion

All four samples were characterized by PXRD, SEM, EDS, and N₂ adsorption at 77.3 K. The PXRD patterns of the samples are shown in Fig. 2b.

All four samples displayed diffraction patterns typical of the PCR zeolite, as reported in literature [36]. No other (crystalline or amorphous) phases were observed in the diffractograms. The SEM images (Fig. 2a) show that each sample is composed of sheet-like, two-dimensional crystals, typical of the PCR zeolite. PCR-1 and PCR-2 contained crystals of various sizes, ranging from submicron fragments to large sheets up to 50 μm in size, PCR-3 and PCR-4 had a narrower crystal size distribution, averaging approximately 15 and 30 μm , respectively. Crystal thickness was approximately 100 nm.

Table 1 summarizes chemical (assessed by EDS) and textural (assessed by N₂ @ 77.3 K adsorption – Fig. S2) properties. Chemical analysis revealed varying amounts of residual germanium from the synthesis (ranging from Si/Ge \approx 40 in PCR-1 to Si/Ge \approx 130 in PCR-3). This germanium content likely reflects highly stable species located within the layers that were not dissolved during the “disassembly” step of the ADOR synthesis, or even other forms, such as GeO₂ impurities (see below for a more detailed discussion). Nevertheless, PXRD showed only the PCR phase. N₂ adsorption revealed differences in the microporosity of the samples, with V_{mic} in the range of 0.09 – 0.12 cm³/g. This difference is significant but within the range previously reported in the literature [36,46,47].

Both propene and propane single-gas adsorption isotherms recorded at 303 K using the routinely used criteria for adsorption equilibrium, i.e., < 0.01% pressure change on 30 s intervals, show a nonlinear concave shape (Fig. 2c). This shape is characteristic of type I adsorption isotherms, according to the IUPAC classification [42]. In all four samples, propene uptake was considerably higher than propane uptake. But in PCR-4, propane uptake was 3 times higher than in the other three PCR samples (< 0.1 mmol/g at atmospheric pressure). So, at least in these three samples, propane was unable to diffuse into the channel system.

Propene uptake differed significantly among the four materials. In PCR-1 and -2, propene uptake at atmospheric pressure ranged from 0.5 to 0.7 mmol/g, reaching approximately 1.2 and 0.9 mmol/g in PCR-3 and PCR-4. Assuming the validity of the Gurvich rule [42], that is, the density of the adsorbed phase is equal to the density of the liquid phase, only 40 – 50% of the PCR-1, -2, and -4 micropores are filled with propene at the highest recorded pressure, in contrast to approximately 80%

Fig. 2. PCR zeolite shows unexpectedly high kinetic selectivity for propene/propane separation. (a) Crystal morphology (SEM images), (b) Phase purity (PXRD patterns), (c) Propene (■) and propane (□) adsorption isotherms (at 303.15 K), (d) Adsorption selectivity (uptake ratio) (at 303 K). PCR-1 – black, PCR-2 – red, PCR-3 – green, PCR-4 – blue.

Table 1
Chemical and textural properties of PCR materials.

Sample	Si/Ge	S _{BET} ^a (m ² /g)	V _{mic} ^b (cm ³ /g)	S _{ex} ^b (m ² /g)
PCR-1	37.8	225	0.088	5.2
PCR-2	58.7	235	0.090	6.7
PCR-3	127.3	259	0.099	2.2
PCR-4	50.0	299	0.117	6.4

^a – calculated in the p/p^o range from zero to the maximum of the Rouquerol function [42].

^b – determined from t-plot using the Harkins-Jura thickness equation.

filled micropores in PCR-3. These differences indicate that the mass transport of both propane and propene is restricted to the channel system of PCR zeolites. The propene/propane selectivity, obtained as the uptake ratio of both gases, is plotted in Fig. 2d.

To more accurately assess the ability of the PCR framework to discriminate between propene and propane, the most (PCR-3) and least (PCR-4) selective materials were further subjected to uptake measurements (Fig. 3a). The results revealed large differences in the diffusivity of propene and propane in both materials. Adsorption was faster in PCR-3 than in PCR-4, in line with its smaller crystal size. Furthermore, when applying the \sqrt{t} -law, the intercept at zero time was nonzero (Fig. 3b), indicating that slow adsorption is preceded by fast uptake of both

Fig. 3. Diffusion measurements reveal strong kinetic discrimination between propene and propane in PCR. (a) Uptake curves fitted with the general model. (b) \sqrt{t} -law analysis. (c) Comparison of apparent diffusivities. PCR-3 – green, PCR-4 – blue; propene – dark, propane – light; ■ – data from general model, □ – data from \sqrt{t} -law; (note: the dashed lines in (b) denote the zero-intercept obtained from the limiting linear fit of the propane uptake curve).

propene and propane within the first seconds of the experiment. This feature was clearly visible in both materials, but was particularly evident in PCR-4, where approximately 53% of propane adsorbs within the first seconds of the experiment.

After fitting the uptake curves to the recommended model (the initial intercepts, as determined from $V(t) = f(\sqrt{t})$ curves, were included in the fitting as fixed values), we calculated the apparent diffusivity of propene and propane. These values were also independently determined employing the \sqrt{t} -law, from the slopes of the tangent lines (see Fig. 3c, Table S1). Both PCR-3 and PCR-4 displayed kinetic selectivity (\equiv diffusivity ratio) in the range of $10^2 - 10^3$ (see Fig. 4c, Table S1). Despite having much faster kinetics, PCR-3 displayed only slightly higher kinetic selectivity than PCR-4, as shown by both models. It should be pointed out, however, that even for the propene – PCR-3 system, which exhibits relatively fast kinetics, full desorption under room temperature conditions has been determined to likely last for hours (see the in-situ propene desorption spectra in Fig. S4), which thus means that regeneration has to involve an increase in the temperature.

The experimental data on propene and propane adsorption on PCR are outlined in Table 2, along with an overview of propene/propane adsorption on small-pore materials with an electroneutral framework.

While the PCR zeolites showed lower propene and propane uptake than previously reported materials, their high propene selectivity was surpassed only by that of CHA [27,28,34,35], DDR [26–28,34], and IHW [29]. PCR-3 matched ITE [27,28] in terms of selectivity and uptake, and all PCR materials showed much higher selectivity than pure-silica ITW [30,49,50], LTA [51], and STT [53] and aluminophosphate zeotypes of both LTA [52] and CHA [48]. To gain further insights into propene and propane adsorption on the PCR framework, we conducted a computational investigation (see the SI for details).

In these simulations (see Fig. 4), we examined four modes of transport of propene and propane, namely, diffusion along the main 10-ring channel ($m \rightarrow m$), diffusion along the side 8-ring channel ($s \rightarrow s$), diffusion from the main 10-ring channel into the 8-ring side channel ($m \rightarrow s$), and diffusion from the 8-ring side channel into the main 10-ring channel ($s \rightarrow m$). Based on the results, all three modes of propene and, especially, propane transport should be considerably hindered in the smaller 8-ring windows, with approximately 530, 250, and 590 propene and propane diffusivity ratios for $s \rightarrow s$, $m \rightarrow s$, and $s \rightarrow m$, respectively. Such propene and propane diffusivity ratios should enable kinetics-based separation of the two hydrocarbon molecules, and they align with experimental values, ranging from 250 to 930, calculated from the uptake curves of the PCR-3 and PCR-4 materials in two independent ways.

Along the main 10-ring channel ($m \rightarrow m$), however, propene and propane transport should not be restricted as the calculated diffusivity ratio was merely 8. This prediction implies that 10-ring channels (and thus the entire channel system) should be fully accessible to both molecules, contradicting the experimental results. Particularly in PCR-4, we observed a second, faster mode of propene and propane transport in the uptake curves (see Fig. 3a and b).

The discrepancy between our computational predictions and experimental results may be explained by a relatively low concentration of foreign species that partly or completely restricts the diffusion of the hydrocarbon molecules in the larger 10-ring channels of PCR. Upon channel blocking, gas separation is only possible thanks to the PCR crystal structure and morphology (see Figs. 1, 2a, and 5). In the two-dimensional structure of the PCR channel system, the pores run parallel along large, sheet-like crystals, with openings strictly on the narrow edges of the large flat crystals.

In a crystal without blockage, both propene and propane should fill the 10-ring channels along their entire length almost instantly.

Fig. 4. Simulations of the ideal PCR framework predict free diffusion of both molecules and contradict the experimental selectivity. (a) Ideal crystal schematic and the investigated diffusion pathways. (b) Computationally determined channel accessibility for fast diffusion. (c) Experimental vs. computational kinetic selectivity comparison (PCR-3 – green, PCR-4 – blue; ■ – data from general model, □ – data from \sqrt{t} -law).

Table 2

Summary of the adsorption performance of PCR samples and related materials reported in the literature.

Sample	Type	$n_{C_3=}$ ^a (mmol/g)	n_{C_3} ^a (mmol/g)	$D_{C_3=}/R^2$ ^b (s ⁻¹)	D_{C_3}/R^2 ^b (s ⁻¹)	$C_3=/C_3$ 1 atm ^c	$C_3=/C_3$ diff ^d	source
PCR-1	PCR	0.67	0.09	-	-	7.4	-	this work
PCR-2	PCR	0.55	0.07	-	-	8.3	-	this work
PCR-3	PCR	1.16	0.10	5.1×10^{-4} ^e	1.3×10^{-6} ^e	11.3	410 ^e	this work
PCR-4	PCR	0.88	0.36	1.2×10^{-5} ^e	4.9×10^{-8} ^e	2.5	250 ^e	this work
AIPO-34	CHA	2.54	2.74	-	-	0.9	~400	[48]
SI-CHA	CHA	2.70 - 2.85	-	4.6×10^{-4}	1.0×10^{-8}	-	46,000	[27,28,34,35]
ITQ-3	ITE	1.50	-	1.5×10^{-3}	2.2×10^{-6}	-	690	[27,28]
ZSM-58	DDR	1.07	-	1.2×10^{-4}	9.6×10^{-9}	-	12,400	[27,28]
DD3R	DDR	1.30	0.08	-	-	15.8	-	[26]
ITQ-12	ITW	1.28	0.50	-	-	2.6	~100	[30,49]
ITW	ITW	1.41	0.68	-	-	2.1	-	[50]
ITQ-32	IHW	1.24	0.40	3.9×10^{-5}	2.7×10^{-8}	3.1	1430	[29]
ITQ-29	LTA	2.37	2.07	-	-	1.1	-	[51]
AIPO-LTA	LTA	2.40	-	-	-	-	~120	[52]
SSZ-23	STT	2.13	2.12	-	-	1.0	-	[53]

^a – uptake at approximately 1 atm, 303 K.^b – apparent diffusivity at approx. 303 K.^c – uptake ratio at approximately 1 atm, 303 K.^d – diffusivity ratio at approximately 303 K.^e – values calculated from the general model fit.

Fig. 5. Defect-induced blockage of 10-ring channels drives selective propene/propane separation in PCR zeolites. (a) The scheme of a perfect PCR crystal without diffusion obstructions (left) and with obstructions (right). (b) Transport pathways of propene vs. propane in obstruction-rich PCR. (c) \sqrt{t} -law analysis of propene (dark blue) and propane (light blue) uptake on PCR-4 (pink and white backgrounds denote 8- and 10-ring limited diffusion, respectively).

Transport through the 8-ring channels, which intersect the main channels, should be significantly slower (the propene and propane diffusivity ratios predicted for $m \rightarrow m$ and $s \rightarrow s$ range from 10^7 to 10^9). Once blocked, the main channels will fill only to the first obstruction, at which point further penetration of hydrocarbon molecules will be limited by

their ability to diffuse through the smaller 8-rings (see Fig. 5a and b). Because PCR crystals are relatively large, pore blockage will have a strong effect even if infrequent.

In our model, the fraction of the unit cells accessible only through the 10-ring channels (diffusion along the direction z) can be calculated as a

function of crystal size and frequency of blocked unit cells using the following formula:

$$f = 2(1 - p)/Np$$

where p stands for the percentage of blocked unit cells, and N for the number of unit cells in the crystal along the z -direction. For example, in a $\sim 20 \mu\text{m}$ square crystal, where only 1 in 400 unit cells blocks the hydrocarbon transport, approximately 95% of the crystal volume is inaccessible to molecules able to diffuse only through the 10-ring channels.

The foreign species or impurities that block the pores are likely formed during the multi-step synthesis of the material, more specifically, when the precursor UTL material remains disassembled into layers. Although these species are unknown, they may theoretically contain either Ge and/or Si, such as extra-framework Ge cations, or amorphous GeO_2 or SiO_2 species. A limited quantity of such species may be plausibly found in pores because the ADOR mechanism involves the hydrolysis of Ge-rich double 4-rings of the UTL zeolite, which releases a large quantity of Ge and Si fragments. A small fraction of these species likely remains between layers even during the subsequent steps of the synthesis.

The mechanism proposed in this study may also apply to other zeolites. For instance, this mechanism may explain adsorption on the RRO (RUB-41) zeolite, which is also prepared by condensation of layers from a 2D precursor (RUB-39) [32]. This framework is highly selective in propene/propane separation [53] despite containing even larger 10-ring channels than the PCR framework. Our hypothesis is also supported by the unusually high concentration of silanol groups in the PCR micropores (Fig. 6a, Table 3), which demonstrates that numerous defects are generated during the multi-step synthesis. Furthermore, these defect sites may serve as binding sites for obstructing species.

As shown in Fig. 6a, in-situ FTIR spectra of all four samples evacuated after a 90-minute treatment at 523 K under dynamic vacuum reveal a broad peak in the O–H vibration region ($\sim 3750\text{--}3200 \text{ cm}^{-1}$). This broad signal is typical of hydrogen-bonded O–H species in pure-silica zeolites and other materials [54–57]. Revealing isolated O–H groups, the signal at 3745 cm^{-1} is also observed in all four samples but is faint, so nearly all hydroxyl groups interact with other hydroxyls or different species. In fact, hydroxyl nests have been detected in other materials

synthesized by ADOR [58].

In our samples, most hydroxyl groups were located within the micropore system, as confirmed by in-situ FTIR with the pivalonitrile probe (see SI for details, Fig. 6b), a Lewis base large enough to avoid diffusion into both 10- and 8-rings. Exposing the material (pre-treated at 523 K for 90 min) to the bulky probe resulted in only marginal changes in the O–H region, providing further evidence that most hydroxyl groups were located in micropores inaccessible to the pivalonitrile probe. In the mesoporous standard SBA-15, by contrast, the strong signal at 3746 cm^{-1} completely disappeared from the spectra, indicating that nearly all hydroxyls interacted with the probe.

The high quantities of silanol groups within the micropores of PCR-3, the best-performing material in the propene/propane separation, were independently verified by ^1H spin-echo solid-state MAS NMR (Fig. 6d–f; for details, see SI). First, spectra of neat PCR-3 (Fig. 6f) revealed a strong band (3.5 ppm) corresponding to silanol groups. Second, coating the material with the bulky $d^{27}\text{-[Eu(fod)}_3]$ shift reagent, which masks the NMR signals of species within a $\sim 10 \text{ nm}$ radius, decreased the intensity of the silanol band by approximately 30% (Fig. 6f). However, this decrease primarily resulted from the planar shape of the crystals (only $\sim 100 \text{ nm}$ thick), whose whole surface and $\sim 20\%$ of the crystal volume were masked by the shift reagent. Most silanol groups ($\sim 70\%$) remained unaffected by the shift reagent and thus were localized deeper within the crystals. The same experiments were also performed with silanol-rich H-FAU (pores inaccessible to the shift reagent) and SBA-15 (pores accessible to the shift reagent), leading to no change and a total change in the silanol signal, respectively (see Fig. 6d and e). These results independently confirm the findings of our FTIR analysis.

To more closely determine the possible chemical nature of the obstructing species, D_3 -acetonitrile adsorption experiments were performed (Fig. 6c). The adsorption of this probe on the PCR zeolites led uniquely to two bands in the ν_2 spectral region of the C–N bond ($2250\text{--}2350 \text{ cm}^{-1}$), namely the signal at 2263 cm^{-1} , identified as D_3 -acetonitrile interacting with the solid by dispersion interactions and a weak shoulder centered around 2275 cm^{-1} , identified with D_3 -acetonitrile interacting with silanols. The lack of a clear signal in the $2305\text{--}2306 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ range (previously reported to correspond to Ge Lewis acid site [59]), or at even higher frequency, likely rules out the presence of a

Fig. 6. Spectroscopic analysis reveals defects. (a) In-situ FTIR spectra of evacuated samples. (b) In-situ FTIR spectra of samples exposed to pivalonitrile (dark = evacuated, light = pivalonitrile-saturated). (c) In-situ FTIR spectra of samples exposed to D_3 -acetonitrile. (PCR-1 = black, PCR-2 = red, PCR-3 = green, PCR-4 = blue, SBA-15 standard = purple, GeO_2 standard = orange). (d) – (f) ^1H spin-echo solid-state MAS NMR spectra (14.1 T) of neat (blue) and impregnated (30 mM shifting/relaxation agent $d^{27}\text{-Eu(fod)}_3$ in $d^2\text{-TCE}$; red) samples of (d) deAl-FAU, (e) SBA-15 and (f) PCR-3.

Table 3

The lattice parameters of the PCR samples (and simulated frameworks), hydroxyl band intensity, and propene/propane adsorptive selectivity indicators.

Sample	a (Å)	b (Å)	c (Å)	β (°)	d (Å)	I_{OH}^{a}	$C_{3=}/C_3$ diff ^{ab}	$C_{3=}/C_3$ 1 atm ^c
PCR-1	20.121	13.962	12.357	114.83	9.130	1.331	-	7.4
PCR-2	20.150	13.950	12.348	114.80	9.146	1.843	-	8.3
PCR-3	20.096	13.962	12.370	115.08	9.101	0.935	410	11.3
PCR-4	20.218	13.904	12.269	114.00	9.235	2.207	250	2.5
PCR-ref[36]	20.114	13.956	12.351	114.80	9.130	-	-	-
PCR-FF ^d	20.029	13.883	12.383	116.35	8.974	-	-	-
PCR-DFT ^d	20.061	14.020	12.439	116.22	8.998	-	-	-

^a – estimated as the ratio of areas under the O–H band (3760–3100 cm^{-1}) and the Si–O overtone band (2090–1755 cm^{-1}).

^b – determined as the ratio of the apparent diffusion coefficients calculated from the general model (infinite sum).

^c – determined as the ratio of the propene and propane uptakes at 800 torr.

^d – obtained from molecular simulations; for details see SI.

meaningful quantity of Ge extra-framework cations or Q^3 framework Ge species. The measurement on the GeO_2 standard revealed that the presence of fully saturated Q^4 framework Ge species doesn't lead to any observable formation of D_3 -acetonitrile in the ν_2 spectral region. Based on this, we consider it likely that the obstructions consist of SiO_2 and/or GeO_2 species. The detected amount of Ge (see Table 1) then tentatively corresponds either to such deposits or to fully incorporated stable Q^4 species in the zeolite framework.

A closer look at the FTIR spectra of the evacuated PCR zeolites (Fig. 6a) reveals marked differences in the intensity of the broad O–H band (centered around 3500 cm^{-1}) across the four samples. The most selective material, PCR-3, displayed the weakest band, whereas the sample with a second, faster process at the onset of adsorption, PCR-4, provided the strongest O–H band (see the relative estimates of O–H band intensity in Table 3 and their correlation with crystallographic parameters in Fig. S3). Assuming that the samples contained similar concentrations of defects, this inverse relationship between propene/propane adsorption selectivity and silanol concentration likely reflects differences in the occupancy of defect sites within the PCR framework.

In PCR-3, the lower concentration of silanol groups indicates a higher occupancy of defect sites by other species, which more strongly restricts propane diffusion into the crystal. Upon entering the main 10-ring channel, the hydrocarbon molecules encounter obstructions sooner and must bypass them through perpendicular 8-ring windows, where propene diffuses approximately 2–3 orders of magnitude faster. In PCR-4, conversely, the high hydroxyl content suggests that fewer defects are blocked by impurities or other species that hinder hydrocarbon transport. As a result, rapid gas uptake during the first seconds of adsorption fills the accessible fraction of 10-ring channels.

To gain deeper insights into these differences between the samples, we determined the lattice parameters of the materials by PXRD in Debye-Scherrer geometry using capillaries (see SI for more details, Fig. S6). Lattice parameters obtained by Le Bail refinement, the corresponding interlayer distances, O–H band intensities (see SI for calculation details) and propene/propane adsorption selectivity indicators are outlined in Table 3.

The interlayer distances of all four zeolites were considerably larger than those predicted by the molecular simulations for an ideal material without defects or impurities (by ~ 0.10 to 0.24 Å), exceeding typical changes caused by adsorption or thermal expansion. This finding further supports our claim that the observed restriction in hydrocarbon adsorption, particularly for propane, cannot arise solely from the framework topology, because the framework dimensions allow propene and propane diffusion without hindrance, especially in the larger 10-ring channels. The increase in interlayer distances likely results from incomplete layer reconnection during the “reassembly” step of the synthesis or from structural expansion induced by foreign species. Since the average interlayer distance correlates with silanol content (see Table 3, Fig. S3), samples with higher silanol concentrations, such as PCR-4, contain more sites with incomplete layer condensation.

4. Conclusions

High-silica PCR zeolites demonstrate high propene selectivity, in stark contrast to computational results, which fail to predict limitations of propane and propene transport through the larger 10-ring channels. This high selectivity of the PCR framework likely derives from the channel-blocking effects within the layers of the material caused by defects or impurities formed during ADOR. These impurities force the hydrocarbon molecules to diffuse through the perpendicularly oriented and smaller 8-ring channels, which selectively restrict propane transport, as computationally predicted (kinetic selectivity on the 8-ring windows: $D_{C_3=}/D_{C_3-} \approx 10^2 - 10^3$) and experimentally observed in volumetric uptake curves of propene and propane on two PCR zeolites. The micropore system of PCR zeolites contains an unusually high concentration of hydroxyl groups, as independently confirmed by in-situ FTIR and NMR. Moreover, slight differences in propene/propane adsorption performance across PCR zeolite batches suggest that defect concentration and distribution may be systematically tuned, most likely during the third step of the ADOR procedure (“organization”), yielding adsorbents with optimal uptake, selectivity, and regenerability for real-world applications in the petroleum industry.

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CRedit authorship contribution statement

Jakub Halamek: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Methodology, Investigation, Data curation. **Tomáš Volný:** Writing – review & editing, Methodology, Investigation. **Roman Bulánek:** Supervision, Project administration, Methodology, Conceptualization. **Jan Blahut:** Methodology, Investigation. **Jiří Čejka:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Project administration. **Pavla Eliášová:** Investigation. **Maksym Opanasenko:** Investigation. **Ota Bludský:** Writing – original draft, Methodology, Investigation, Conceptualization.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Supplementary materials

Supplementary material associated with this article can be found, in the online version, at [10.1016/j.ceja.2026.101229](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ceja.2026.101229).

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

References

- R.B. Eldridge, Olefin/paraffin separation technology: a review, *Ind. Eng. Chem. Res.* 32 (10) (1993) 2208–2212, <https://doi.org/10.1021/ie00022a002>.
- J.A. Moulijn, M. Makkee, A.E. van Diepen, *Chemical Process Technology*, 2nd ed., John Wiley & Sons Ltd., Chichester, West Sussex, UK, 2013.
- D.S. Sholl, R.P. Lively, Seven chemical separations to change the world, *Nature* 532 (7600) (2016) 435–437, <https://doi.org/10.1038/532435a>.
- X. Huang, F. Chen, H. Sun, L. Yang, Q. Yang, Z. Zhang, Y. Yang, Q. Ren, Z. Bao, Quasi-discrete pore engineering via Ligand racemization in metal–Organic frameworks for thermodynamic–Kinetic synergistic separation of propylene and propane, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* 146 (1) (2024) 617–626, <https://doi.org/10.1021/jacs.3c10495>.
- Y.-S. Wang, X.-J. Zhang, Y.-Q. Ba, T.-Y. Li, G.-P. Hao, A.-H. Lu, Recent advances in carbon-based adsorbents for adsorptive separation of light hydrocarbons, *Research* 2022 (2022), <https://doi.org/10.34133/2022/9780864>.
- R.-B. Lin, Z. Zhang, B. Chen, Achieving high performance metal–Organic framework materials through pore engineering, *Acc. Chem. Res.* 54 (17) (2021) 3362–3376, <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.accounts.1c00328>.
- M. Bergaoui, M. Khalfaoui, A. Awadallah-F, S. Al-Muhtaseb, A review of the features and applications of ZIF-8 and its derivatives for separating CO₂ and isomers of C₃- and C₄- hydrocarbons, *J. Nat. Gas. Sci. Eng.* 96 (2021) 104289, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jngse.2021.104289>.
- E. Pérez-Botella, S. Valencia, F. Rey, Zeolites in adsorption processes: state of the art and future prospects, *Chem. Rev.* 122 (24) (2022) 17647–17695, <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.chemrev.2c00140>.
- M. Gehre, Z. Guo, G. Rothenberg, S. Tanase, Sustainable separations of C₄-hydrocarbons by using microporous materials, *ChemSusChem* 10 (20) (2017) 3947–3963, <https://doi.org/10.1002/cssc.201700657>.
- Y. Wang, S.B. Peh, D. Zhao, Alternatives to cryogenic distillation: advanced porous materials in adsorptive light olefin/paraffin separations, *Small* 15 (25) (2019) 1900058, <https://doi.org/10.1002/smll.201900058>.
- Y. Wu, B.M. Weckhuysen, Separation and purification of hydrocarbons with porous materials, *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed.* 60 (35) (2021) 18930–18949, <https://doi.org/10.1002/anie.202104318>.
- C.A. Grande, C. Gigola, A.E. Rodrigues, Propane–Propylene binary adsorption on Zeolite 4A, *Adsorption* 9 (4) (2003) 321–329, <https://doi.org/10.1023/A:1026223914143>.
- F.A. Da Silva, A.E. Rodrigues, Adsorption equilibria and kinetics for propylene and propane over 13X and 4A zeolite pellets, *Ind. Eng. Chem. Res.* 38 (5) (1999) 2051–2057, <https://doi.org/10.1021/ie980640z>.
- J. Padin, S.U. Rege, R.T. Yang, L.S. Cheng, Molecular sieve sorbents for kinetic separation of propane/propylene, *Chem. Eng. Sci.* 55 (20) (2000) 4525–4535, [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0009-2509\(00\)00099-3](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0009-2509(00)00099-3).
- H. Jarvelin, J.R. Fair, Adsorptive separation of propylene-propane mixtures, *Ind. Eng. Chem. Res.* 32 (10) (1993) 2201–2207, <https://doi.org/10.1021/ie00022a001>.
- S. Divekar, A. Nanoti, S. Dasgupta, Aarti, R. Chauhan, P. Gupta, M.O. Garg, S. P. Singh, I.M. Mishra, Adsorption equilibria of propylene and propane on zeolites and prediction of their binary Adsorption with the ideal adsorbed solution theory, *J. Chem. Eng. Data* 61 (7) (2016) 2629–2637, <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.jced.6b00294>.
- M. Mofarahi, S.M. Salehi, Pure and binary adsorption isotherms of ethylene and ethane on zeolite 5A, *Adsorption* 19 (1) (2013) 101–110, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10450-012-9423-1>.
- S. Aguado, G. Bergeret, C. Daniel, D. Farrusseng, Absolute molecular sieve separation of ethylene/ethane mixtures with silver zeolite A, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* 134 (36) (2012) 14635–14637, <https://doi.org/10.1021/ja305663k>.
- A. Van Miltenburg, W. Zhu, F. Kapteijn, J.A. Moulijn, Adsorptive separation of light olefin/paraffin mixtures, *Chem. Eng. Res. Des.* 84 (5) (2006) 350–354, <https://doi.org/10.1205/cherd05021>.
- R.T. Yang, E.S. Kikkides, New sorbents for olefin/paraffin separations by adsorption via π -complexation, *AIChE J.* 41 (3) (1995) 509–517, <https://doi.org/10.1002/aic.690410309>.
- A. Jayaraman, R.T. Yang, C.L. Munson, D. Chinn, Deactivation of π -complexation adsorbents by hydrogen and rejuvenation by oxidation, *Ind. Eng. Chem. Res.* 40 (20) (2001) 4370–4376, <https://doi.org/10.1021/ie0102753>.
- A. Takahashi, R.T. Yang, C.L. Munson, D. Chinn, Cu(I)–Y-zeolite as a superior adsorbent for diene/Olefin separation, *Langmuir* 17 (26) (2001) 8405–8413, <https://doi.org/10.1021/la011196z>.
- E. Koudelková, Y. Ghrib, F.S. de Oliveira Ramos, P. Čičmanec, R. Bulánek, Adsorption and separation of the C₃ hydrocarbons on cationic FER zeolites: effect of dual sites existence, *Microporous Mesoporous Mater.* 279 (2019) 416–422, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.micromeso.2019.01.032>.
- A. Anson, C.C.H. Lin, T.M. Kuznicki, S.M. Kuznicki, Separation of ethylene/ethane mixtures by adsorption on small-pored titanasilicate molecular sieves, *Chem. Eng. Sci.* 65 (2) (2010) 807–811, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ces.2009.09.033>.
- A. Anson, Y. Wang, C.C.H. Lin, T.M. Kuznicki, S.M. Kuznicki, Adsorption of ethane and ethylene on modified ETS-10, *Chem. Eng. Sci.* 63 (16) (2008) 4171–4175, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ces.2008.05.038>.
- J. Gascon, W. Blom, A. van Miltenburg, A. Ferreira, R. Berger, F. Kapteijn, Accelerated synthesis of all-silica DD3R and its performance in the separation of propylene/propane mixtures, *Microporous Mesoporous Mater.* 115 (3) (2008) 585–593, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.micromeso.2008.02.038>.
- D.H. Olson, Light hydrocarbon separation using 8-member ring zeolites, US 6488741 B2 (2002).
- D.H. Olson, M.A. Cambor, L.A. Villaescusa, G.H. Kuehl, Light hydrocarbon sorption properties of pure silica Si-CHA and ITQ-3 and high silica ZSM-58, *Microporous Mesoporous Mater.* 67 (1) (2004) 27–33, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.micromeso.2003.09.025>.
- M. Palomino, A. Cantín, A. Corma, S. Leiva, F. Rey, S. Valencia, Pure silica ITQ-32 zeolite allows separation of linear olefins from paraffins, *Chem. Commun.* (12) (2007) 1233–1235, <https://doi.org/10.1039/B700358G>.
- D.H. Olson, X. Yang, M.A. Cambor, ITQ-12: A zeolite having temperature dependent adsorption selectivity and potential for propene separation, *J. Phys. Chem. B* 108 (30) (2004) 11044–11048, <https://doi.org/10.1021/jp040216d>.
- P.J. Bereciartua, Á. Cantín, A. Corma, J.L. Jordá, M. Palomino, F. Rey, S. Valencia, E.W. Corcoran, P. Kortunov, P.I. Ravikovitch, A. Burton, C. Yoon, Y. Wang, C. Paur, J. Guzman, A.R. Bishop, G.L. Casty, Control of zeolite framework flexibility and pore topology for separation of ethane and ethylene, *Science* 358 (6366) (2017) 1068–1071, <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.aao092>.
- Y.X. Wang, H. Gies, B. Marler, U. Müller, Synthesis and crystal structure of Zeolite RUB-41 obtained as calcination product of a layered precursor: a systematic approach to a new Synthesis route, *Chem. Mater.* 17 (1) (2005) 43–49, <https://doi.org/10.1021/cm048677z>.
- N. De Witte, S. Robijns, J.F.M. Denayer, M. Dusselier, T.R.C. Van Assche, Inverse gas chromatography study of n-alkane and 1-alkene adsorption on pure-silica LTA (ITQ-29) and CHA, *J. Phys. Chem. C* 127 (50) (2023) 24393–24402, <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.jpcc.3c05698>.
- N. Hedin, G.J. DeMartin, W.J. Roth, K.G. Strohmaier, S.C. Reyes, PFG NMR self-diffusion of small hydrocarbons in high silica DDR, CHA and LTA structures, *Microporous Mesoporous Mater.* 109 (1) (2008) 327–334, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.micromeso.2007.05.007>.
- H. Maghsoudi, H. Abdi, A. Aidani, Temperature- and pressure-dependent adsorption equilibria and diffusivities of propylene and propane in pure-silica Si-CHA zeolite, *Ind. Eng. Chem. Res.* 59 (4) (2020) 1682–1692, <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.iecr.9b05451>.
- W.J. Roth, P. Nachtigall, R.E. Morris, P.S. Wheatley, V.R. Seymour, S.E. Ashbrook, P. Chlubná, L. Grajciar, M. Položij, A. Zukal, O. Shvets, J. Čejka, A family of zeolites with controlled pore size prepared using a top-down method, *Nat. Chem* 5 (7) (2013) 628–633, <https://doi.org/10.1038/nchem.1662>.
- J.-L. Paillaud, B. Harbuzaru, J. Patarin, N. Bats, Extra-large-pore zeolites with two-dimensional channels formed by 14 and 12 rings, *Science* 304 (5673) (2004) 990–992, <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.1098242>.
- A. Corma, M.J. Díaz-Cabañas, F. Rey, S. Nicolopoulos, K. Boulahya, ITQ-15: the first ultralarge pore zeolite with a bi-directional pore system formed by intersecting 14- and 12-ring channels, and its catalytic implications, *Chem. Commun.* (12) (2004) 1356–1357, <https://doi.org/10.1039/B406572G>.
- P.S. Wheatley, P. Chlubná-Eliášová, H. Greer, W. Zhou, V.R. Seymour, D. M. Dawson, S.E. Ashbrook, A.B. Pinar, L.B. McCusker, M. Opanasenko, J. Čejka, R. E. Morris, Zeolites with continuously tuneable porosity, *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed.* 53 (48) (2014) 13210–13214, <https://doi.org/10.1002/anie.201407676>.
- P. Eliášová, M. Opanasenko, P.S. Wheatley, M. Shamzhy, M. Mazur, P. Nachtigall, W.J. Roth, R.E. Morris, J. Čejka, The ADOR mechanism for the synthesis of new zeolites, *Chem. Soc. Rev* 44 (20) (2015) 7177–7206, <https://doi.org/10.1039/C5CS00045A>.
- International Zeolite Association, Database of Zeolite structures. https://europe.iza-structure.org/IZA-SC/ftc_table.php, 2026 (Accessed 1/1/2026).
- M. Thommes, K. Kaneko, A.V. Neimark, J.P. Olivier, F. Rodriguez-Reinoso, J. Rouquerol, K.S.W. Sing, Physisorption of gases, with special reference to the evaluation of surface area and pore size distribution (IUPAC Technical Report), 87 (9–10) (2015) 1051–1069, <https://doi.org/10.1515/pac-2014-1117>.
- J. Kärger, R. Valiullin, S. Brandani, J. Caro, C. Chmelik, B.F. Chmelka, M.-O. Coppens, S. Farooq, D. Freude, H. Jobic, M. Kruteva, E. Mangano, R. Pini, W.S. Price, A. Rajendran, P.I. Ravikovitch, G. Sastre, R.Q. Snurr, A.G. Stepanov, S. Vasenkov, Y. Wang, B.M. Weckhuysen, Diffusion in nanoporous materials with special consideration of the measurement of determining parameters (IUPAC Technical Report), 97(1) (2025) 1–89, <https://doi.org/10.1515/pac-2023-1126>.

- [44] J. Kärger, Determination of diffusion coefficients in porous Media, in: G. Ertl, H. Knözinger, F. Schüth, J. Weitkampf (Eds.), *Handbook of Heterogeneous Catalysis*, Wiley-VCH Verlag GmbH, Weinheim, 2008, pp. 1714–1727.
- [45] E. Beerdsen, B. Smit, D. Dubbeldam, Molecular simulation of loading dependent slow diffusion in confined systems, *Phys. Rev. Lett.* 93 (24) (2004) 248301, <https://doi.org/10.1103/PhysRevLett.93.248301>.
- [46] Y. Zhou, S.A. Kadam, M. Shamzhy, J. Čejka, M. Opanasenko, Isoreticular UTL-derived zeolites as model materials for probing pore size–Activity relationship, *ACS. Catal.* 9 (6) (2019) 5136–5146, <https://doi.org/10.1021/acscatal.9b00950>.
- [47] A. Zukal, M. Shamzhy, M. Kubů, J. Čejka, The effect of pore size dimensions in isoreticular zeolites on carbon dioxide adsorption heats, *J. CO2 Util.* 24 (2018) 157–163, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jcou.2017.12.016>.
- [48] S.C. Reyes, V.V. Krishnan, G.J. Demartin, J.H. Sinfelt, K.G. Strohmaier, J.G. Santiesteban, Separation of propylene from hydrocarbon mixtures, US 6730142 B2 (2004).
- [49] P.A. Barrett, T. Boix, M. Puche, D.H. Olson, E. Jordan, H. Koller, M.A. Cambor, ITQ-12: a new microporous silica polymorph potentially useful for light hydrocarbon separations, *Chem. Commun.* (17) (2003) 2114, <https://doi.org/10.1039/B306440A>.
- [50] J.G. Min, A. Luna-Triguero, Y. Byun, S.R.G. Balestra, J.M. Vicent-Luna, S. Calero, S. B. Hong, M.A. Cambor, Stepped propane adsorption in pure-silica ITW Zeolite, *Langmuir* 34 (16) (2018) 4774–4779, <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.langmuir.8b00628>.
- [51] N. Hedin, G.J. DeMartin, K.G. Strohmaier, S.C. Reyes, PFG NMR self-diffusion of propylene in ITQ-29, CaA and NaCaA: window size and cation effects, *Microporous Mesoporous Mater.* 98 (1) (2007) 182–188, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.micromeso.2006.08.017>.
- [52] F. Hibbe, J. Caro, C. Chmelik, A. Huang, T. Kirchner, D. Ruthven, R. Valiullin, J. Kärger, Monitoring molecular mass transfer in cation-free nanoporous host crystals of type AlPO-LTA, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* 134 (18) (2012) 7725–7732, <https://doi.org/10.1021/ja211492b>.
- [53] T.D. Pham, R.F. Lobo, Adsorption equilibria of CO2 and small hydrocarbons in AEI-, CHA-, STT-, and RRO-type siliceous zeolites, *Microporous Mesoporous Mater.* 236 (2016) 100–108, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.micromeso.2016.08.025>.
- [54] A. Zecchina, S. Bordiga, G. Spoto, L. Marchese, G. Petrini, G. Leofanti, M. Padovan, Silicalite characterization. 1. Structure, adsorptive capacity, and IR spectroscopy of the framework and hydroxyl modes, *J. Phys. Chem.* 96 (12) (1992) 4985–4990, <https://doi.org/10.1021/j100191a047>.
- [55] A. Zecchina, S. Bordiga, G. Spoto, L. Marchese, G. Petrini, G. Leofanti, M. Padovan, Silicalite characterization. 2. IR spectroscopy of the interaction of carbon monoxide with internal and external hydroxyl groups, *J. Phys. Chem.* 96 (12) (1992) 4991–4997, <https://doi.org/10.1021/j100191a048>.
- [56] R.S. McDonald, Surface functionality of amorphous silica by infrared spectroscopy, *J. Phys. Chem.* 62 (10) (1958) 1168–1178, <https://doi.org/10.1021/j150568a004>.
- [57] A. Burneau, O. Barres, J.P. Gallas, J.C. Lavalley, Comparative study of the surface hydroxyl groups of fumed and precipitated silicas. 2. Characterization by infrared spectroscopy of the interactions with water, *Langmuir* 6 (8) (1990) 1364–1372, <https://doi.org/10.1021/la00098a008>.
- [58] A. Li, Y. Zhang, C.J. Heard, K. Gołabek, X. Ju, J. Čejka, M. Mazur, Encapsulating metal nanoparticles into a layered zeolite precursor with surface silanol nests enhances sintering resistance, *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed.* 62 (1) (2023) e202213361, <https://doi.org/10.1002/anie.202213361>.
- [59] S. Abdi, M. Kubů, A. Li, K. Kalíková, M. Shamzhy, Addressing confinement effect in alkenes epoxidation using ‘isoreticular’ titanosilicate zeolite catalysts, *Catal. Today* 390-391 (2022) 326–334, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cattod.2021.09.027>.